

Supporting Information

Synthesis of Hollow Spherical Phosphide Catalysts with Industrial-Scale Potential for Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution Reaction

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2. Experimental

2.1 Chemical and Materials

The source compounds for the preparation of phosphides included: ammonium phosphate dibasic ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (Centralchem, 99%), iron (III) nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Centralchem, 98%), cobalt (II) nitrate hexahydrate $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Centralchem, 99%), nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Centralchem, 98%), ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Centralchem, 99%), citric acid $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$ (Centralchem, 99.5%). For electrochemical performance analysis, potassium hydroxide (KOH, Centralchem, 85%) was used as the electrolyte and Platinum on carbon (PtC, Sigma-Aldrich, $M_w = 195.08 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) and Iridium oxide (IrO_2 , Sigma-Aldrich, $M_w = 224.22 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) were used as standard catalysts.

Fig. S1 Drying device TEFIC Biotech; TFS-2L used for the preparation of phosphide precursors

Fig. S2 MoFeP, MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP (A) powder precursors after spray drying (B) powders after calcination in a reducing atmosphere of H₂ at 650 °C

2.2 Structural methods and characterization

The scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL, JSM-7000F, Japan) and transmission electron microscope (TEM, HRTEM, SAED, JEOL, JEM-2100F, Japan) were used for morphology visualisation. The phase composition of the samples was realized by XRD analysis (PhilipsX' PertPro) using the X'Pert Pro (Philips) diffractometer equipped with Cu K α radiation, operating at 40 kV and 50 mA. The patterns were recorded at the 2 theta range between 10 and 60°. For evaluation of the thermal degradation, Differential thermal analysis (DTA)/Thermogravimetric analysis (TG) using simultaneous thermal analyser NETZSCH STA449F3 Jupiter at a heating rate of 10 °C.min⁻¹ up to 1200 °C in Al₂O₃ crucible under air/argon atmosphere. The samples were processed in a vacuum before analysis.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out using a custom-built spectrometer (SPECS Surface Nano Analysis GmbH, Germany) operating under ultra-high vacuum conditions (2×10^{-9} mbar). The system was equipped with a high-intensity, monochromated, micro-focused Al K α X-ray source (SPECS μ -FOCUS 600) and a multichannel electron energy analyzer (PHOIBOS 150 NAP 1D-DLD). Samples were pressed into pellets and mounted on a stainless-steel holder using a stainless-steel strip. Low-resolution survey spectra were recorded with an acquisition step size of 1 eV (pass energy of 50 eV). Detailed XPS regions (Fe 2p, Mo 2p, Co 2p, Ni 2p, O 1s, C 1s, and P 2p) were acquired with an acquisition step size of 0.05 eV (pass energy of 20 eV). Deconvolution of

detailed spectra was performed using KolXPD (1.8.0) software. A Shirley background and Voigt profiles were used for deconvolution. All 2p components were fitted with the ratio of $p_{3/2} : p_{1/2}$ peak intensities fixed at 2 : 1. Analogously, intensities of $3d_{5/2}$ and $3d_{3/2}$ peaks in 3d peaks were fixed at 3 : 2. The binding energies (BE) were adjusted using the main adventitious sp^3 carbon peak referenced at 284.9 eV. The charging correction was in all cases about 1.1 eV, suggesting reasonable electronic conductivity of the samples.

Fig. S3 Survey X-ray photoelectron spectra of investigated samples

Fig. S4 Detailed X-ray photoelectron C1s spectra of investigated samples with deconvolution.

2.3 Electrochemical characterization

The electrochemical experiments were conducted using a Vionic potentiostat/galvanostat (Metrohm, Switzerland). The potential was calculated with respect to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) according to Eq.(1).

$$E_{\text{vs RHE}} = E_{\text{vs Ag/AgCl}} + E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.0591 \times \text{pH} \quad (\text{S1})$$

Table S1 Values of overpotentials at current densities of -10, -20, and -50 mA.cm⁻² (η_{-10} , η_{-20} , η_{-50}) and Tafel slopes (b) in 1 M KOH for all samples

Sample	η_{-10} [mV]	η_{-20} [mV]	η_{-50} [mV]	b [mV dec ⁻¹]
Pt RDE	-100	-128	-178	51
MoFeCoP	-258	-292	-357	82
MoFeP	-337	-372	-440	92
MoFeNiP	-421	-467	-554	89
GCE	-718	-756	-851	112

Fig. S5 The circuits used for fitting EIS measurements in 1M KOH

The double-layer capacitance of real electrode-electrolyte interfaces is often well described by a Constant Phase Element (CPE) instead of a simple capacitor. CPE has impedance Z_{CPE} defined by the Eq. 2:

$$Z_{CPE} = (1/Y_0)/(j\omega)^\alpha \quad (S2)$$

where Y_0 and α ($\alpha \leq 1$) are CPE constants and ω is angular velocity. When $\alpha = 1$, then CPE behaves like a capacitor with capacitance C , i.e. $Y^0 = C$.

χ^2 indicates an error in EIS fit

The double layer capacitance (Cdl) values were determined using the cyclic voltammetry (CV) method at scan rates of 20, 50, 100, 200, and 400 mV/s. The electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) of the samples is typically estimated using a simple CV approach. The ECSA of a catalyst sample is calculated from the the double layer capacitance (Cdl) according to Eq S3:

$$ECSA = \frac{C_{dl}}{C_s} \quad (S3)$$

However, determining the exact surface area of the material is challenging due to the unknown capacitive behavior (C_s) of the specific catalysts. Nevertheless, relative surface areas can be reliably estimated, as the Cdl is expected to be linearly proportional to the effective active surface area. The Cdl is determined by plotting the charging current density around the open circuit potential (Δj), calculated according to Eq. S4 against the scan rate.

$$\Delta j = (j_a - j_c)/2 \quad (S4)$$

j_a and j_c are oxidation and reduction current density at open circuit potential, respectively.

Effective differential capacitance C_{eff} of a circuit consisting of parallelly connected resistor (with resistance R_p) and CPE (with impedance Z_{CPE}) can be calculated using the formula:

$$C_{eff} = Y_0 \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right) R_p \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}-1\right) \quad (S5)$$

Fig. S6 CV for ECSA measured for fibrous samples in 1M KOH

Recalculation of the potentials measured with respect to Ag/AgCl reference electrode (at temperature T), i.e. $E^T_{\text{vs Ag/AgCl}}$ to RHE scale (at temperature T), i.e. $E^T_{\text{vs RHE}}$:

$$E^T_{\text{vs RHE}} = E^T_{\text{vs Ag/AgCl}} + E^T_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(10) \text{ pH} \quad (\text{S6})$$

$E^T_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$ values can be found in Table S2

Table S2. Standard potential of reference $E^T_{\text{Ag/AgCl, 3 M KCl}}$ electrode vs RHE with increasing temperature [1].

T [K]	$E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$ [V]
298.15	0.207
303.15	0.2034
308.15	0.1998
313.15	0.1961
318.15	0.1923
323.15	0.1884
328.15	0.1844
333.15	0.1803

[1] <https://www.meinsberger-elektroden.de/en/ueberblick/potential.html>

Fig. S7 LSV curves for (a) MoFeNiP and (b) MoFeCoP at different temperatures in 1 M KOH. Tafel plots for (c) MoFeNiP and (d) MoFeCoP derived from the LSV curves at various temperatures, scan rate 10 mV s⁻¹.